

Einstein from kids

Adolf Cusmariu

adolcus@gmail.com

The Pythagorean Theorem applied to the Einstein triangle

illustrates the famous mass-energy-momentum-lightspeed formula of Special Relativity:

$$E^2 = p^2c^2 + m^2c^4$$

Rewrite this as a quadratic equation in a 'variable' C^2 :

$$m^2(c^2)^2 + p^2c^2 - E^2 = 0$$

which is solved by

$$c^2_1 = (-p^2 + (p^4 + 4m^2E^2)^{1/2})/2m^2$$

$$c^2_2 = (-p^2 - (p^4 + 4m^2E^2)^{1/2})/2m^2$$

Thus

$$c^2_1 + c^2_2 = -p^2/m^2$$

and

$$c^2_1c^2_2 = -E^2/m^2$$

Now, the lightspeed C can only be real, implying both momentum p and energy E must then be purely imaginary in this setting, or mass m must be so; unphysical results of course.

Thus C^2 cannot be a variable here; therefore the lightspeed C itself must be a constant, independent of mass, energy, and momentum.